

First principles study of oxidation resistance of amorphous Si-(B)-C-N materials, and experimental verification

Jemal Yimer Damte^{*}

Department of Physics and NTIS – European Centre of Excellence, University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, Univerzitni 8 30614 Plzen, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

SiBCN
Thin films
Oxidation
Activation energy
Ab-initio

ABSTRACT

Amorphous silicon boron carbonitride (Si-B-C-N) ceramics offer superior oxidation resistance at high temperatures. These ceramics are excellent candidates for use as coatings in high-temperature applications and other advanced technologies. We investigate the oxidation resistance of amorphous Si-(B)-C-N ceramic materials in a wide range of elemental compositions using density functional theory. We go beyond the empirical experimental results and focus on complete quantitative description of the oxidation onset in terms of the corresponding reaction energies. Several adsorption sites are explored to examine the adsorption behavior of O₂ molecules and to identify the most stable adsorption configuration at each surface. Next, we analyze O₂ dissociation by examining intermediate configurations at the most stable adsorption sites. We obtain energy barriers of 2.13–3.27 eV (Si-B-C-N) and 1.41–1.53 eV (Si-C-N), in both cases increasing with increasing Si/C ratio. These findings align well with our qualitative experimental results, quantify them, and facilitate the comparison of Si-(B)-C-N ceramics with other materials and the full utilization of their application potential.

1. Introduction

Amorphous Si-(B)-C-N alloys are of worldwide interest [1–11] due to a combination of (i) oxidation resistance and thermal stability up to exceptionally high temperatures with (ii) preservance of useful functional properties up to these temperatures [12–17]. Examples of specific achievements include oxidation resistance up to 1500 °C [1], thermal stability of the amorphous networks up to 1700 °C [2], stable high hardness up to 1500 °C [18] or stable refractive index of transparent compositions up to 1400 °C [19] (temperatures above those referred to as ultra-high [20,21]). The space of achievable properties (mechanical [22], optical [23], electrical [24], photodetection [25], photoluminescence [5], absorption of EM waves [14] or piezoresistivity [15]) is wide as well. This makes these alloys attractive for many applications ranging from high-temperature electronics through high-temperature protective coatings to sensors for harsh environment [26–28]. While the interest in the oxidation resistance is a long-time but ongoing [29,30], the interest in a broadband and/or high-temperature absorption of EM waves [14,31,32], often using composites combining Si-B-C-N with C nanotubes or nanofibers [33–35] or aerogels combining Si-B-C-N with SiC or Al₂O₃ [36,37] constitutes one of the hot subtopics. Further widening of the space of achievable properties by incorporating

transition metals such as Zr or Hf has been considered as well [38–40].

However, there is an important knowledge gap. On the one hand, the crucial oxidation resistance has been investigated experimentally for bulk materials as well as thin films. Significant variations of the oxidation onset have been revealed (let alone the variations of the oxidation rate at temperatures above the onset, which is relatively less important for the present work). First, a low boron content (below 16.7 %) significantly contributes to the oxidation resistance of amorphous Si-B-C-N ceramic materials [41–47], which in turn exhibit better oxidation resistance than Si-C-N materials [4,48–50]. Second, high Si/C ratio further enhances the oxidation resistance of amorphous Si-(B)-C-N ceramics compared to a low Si/C ratio [4,51]. On the other hand, there is a lack of information about the atomic-scale processes which take place at Si-(B)-C-N surfaces of various compositions (before a protective oxide layer forms) and which control whether the material starts to oxidize at a given temperature. In the first place, the corresponding energy barriers have not been quantified yet.

The experimental interest in Si-B-C-N materials is complemented by increasingly powerful *ab initio* calculations [18,51–54]. To reinforce the experimental findings on the oxidation resistance of amorphous Si-(B)-C-N ceramic materials, this paper presents *ab initio* calculations of the activation energy barrier for the oxidation process involving O₂

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: damtejem@ntis.zcu.cz (J.Y. Damte).

molecules on the surfaces of these materials. We investigate the barrier for oxidation by O₂ for the surfaces of Si-(B)-C-N ceramic materials with varying Si/C ratios and with or without boron, using density functional theory (DFT). These DFT calculations are complemented by and support our experimental results on the oxidation resistance of Si-(B)-C-N thin films. The results provide valuable insights into the fundamental mechanisms underlying the material's resistance to oxidation, thereby further quantifying the experimental findings. By analyzing the activation energy barriers, we can more accurately predict the performance of Si-(B)-C-N ceramics under extreme conditions, enhancing their potential for high-temperature applications.

2. Computational details

In our previous work [54], we predicted amorphous Si-(B)-C-N structures using a modified liquid quench algorithm. This algorithm captures the formation conditions of materials resulting from the rapid cooling of the localized melt created around sites of energetic ion impact, taking the formation and loss of unbonded N₂ molecules into account. The simulations were performed using DFT implemented in the CPMD code [55]. The presented bonding statistics have been calculated using a representation of pairs of valence electrons by centers of maximally localized Wannier functions (WFCs; localized orbitals, obtained by a transformation of Bloch orbitals calculated using DFT). Multiple bonds are characterized by multiple WFCs between the same two atoms.

All present calculations were performed using DFT implemented in the VASP package [56]. The Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional within the Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA) was employed to handle exchange–correlation energy [57]. To describe the interactions between core and valence electrons, the Projector Augmented Wave (PAW) method was used [58]. A cutoff energy of 400 eV was applied for the plane wave basis, and a 5 × 5 × 1 k-point grid was used in the Monkhorst–Pack scheme. A vacuum thickness of 15 Å was introduced to separate the surface from its periodic images along the z-direction.

The calculations yielded the following quantities. First, the adsorption energy (E_{ads}) of the intermediates on the surface was calculated using the formula.

$$E_{\text{ads}} = E_{\text{surface/molecule}} - E_{\text{surface}} - E_{\text{molecule}}$$

where $E_{\text{surface/molecule}}$ is the total energy of surface together with a molecule, E_{surface} is the energy of a clean surface and E_{molecule} is the calculated energy of a molecule. Next, the Climbing Image Nudged Elastic Band (CI-NEB) method [59] was employed to describe the O₂ dissociation, through the transition state having the highest energy along the reaction coordinate (E_{max}) to the final stable state having the minimum energy (E_{final}). These quantities are behind the crucial activation energy (E_{act}) calculated as

$$E_{\text{act}} = E_{\text{max}} - E_{\text{ads}}$$

and also behind the reaction energy (E_{react}) calculated as

$$E_{\text{react}} = E_{\text{final}} - E_{\text{ads}}$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. List of compositions investigated

The effects of (i) different Si/C ratios and (ii) presence or absence of boron in amorphous alloys of silicon, boron, carbon, and nitrogen have been analyzed. Specifically, the eight compositions investigated include Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄, Si₂₈B₉C₁₂N₅₃, Si₂₃B₁₁C₁₉N₄₉, Si₂₀B₁₁C₂₆N₄₃, Si₁₅B₁₃C₃₃N₃₇, Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆, Si₄₀C₆N₅₄, and Si₁₁C₅₃N₃₆. The extremal compositions Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄ and Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆ as well as their atomic

densities are based on our previous experiments using reactive magnetron sputtering [4] (one side-effect of varied Si/C ratio is a different affinity to N and different maximum achievable N content [60]), the compositions with other Si/C ratios represent linear combinations of the extremal ones, and the Si-C-N compositions were obtained by replacing B by Si at high Si/C and by C at low Si/C.

The bonding statistics characterizing these amorphous networks (before creating the surfaces by cutting them) are summarized in Table 1, together with the corresponding densities. While in the present paper this is only a starting point, in some of our previous papers the bonding statistics represent a result on their own. To put one example, the non-negligible concentration of carbon–carbon bonds at Si/C ratio below ≈1 is crucial for the electrical conductivity (the highest occupied electronic states are significantly localized on them, see [54] for details).

3.2. Adsorption geometry of oxygen molecule on amorphous Si-(B)-C-N

The equilibrium geometry of intermediates on a surface is a basis of all surface phenomena. Unlike crystalline surfaces, identifying high-symmetry adsorption sites on amorphous ceramic materials is challenging. Therefore, in this study, different sites were considered to understand the adsorption behavior and determine the stable adsorption site for an O₂ molecule. In parallel, we considered two different approaches before the start of geometry optimization: the vertical approach, where O₂ is perpendicular to the surface with one oxygen atom closer to the surface than the other, and the parallel approach, where O₂ lies flat along the surface. The optimized geometries and adsorption energies are shown in Fig. 1 and Table 2, respectively.

Fig. 1 depicts the most stable geometry for O₂ adsorption on Si-(B)-C-N, obtained after evaluating several different sites. We found that for all vertical approaches, the absolute values of adsorption energies were lower compared to the corresponding parallel approaches, except on the Si-rich surface Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄. This is the first fingerprint of the fact that the structural and compositional differences within the Si-(B)-C-N ceramic materials significantly influence the adsorption behavior of O₂ molecules. The aforementioned surface Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄ at the same time exhibits the largest E_{ads} of O₂ among the amorphous materials considered in this study, −4.43 eV.

Furthermore, Fig. 1(a) shows that O₂ molecule prefers to adsorb on top of a nitrogen atom in this case, at the shortest geometric distance of 1.34 Å. The E_{ads} values on all surfaces Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄, Si₂₈B₉C₁₂N₅₃, Si₂₃B₁₁C₁₉N₄₉, Si₂₀B₁₁C₂₆N₄₃, Si₁₅B₁₃C₃₃N₃₇, Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆, Si₄₀C₆N₅₄, and Si₁₁C₅₃N₃₆ (Fig. 1a–h, respectively) are −4.43 eV, −2.40 eV, −2.63 eV, −2.06 eV, −3.05 eV, −3.70 eV, −4.32 eV and −1.19 eV, respectively. While these energies themselves do not yet yield convincing monotonic dependencies, they are a basis of monotonic dependencies of $E_{\text{act}} = E_{\text{max}} - E_{\text{ads}}$ shown next.

3.3. Oxygen molecule dissociation on amorphous Si-(B)-C-N surfaces

Following the adsorption of an O₂ molecule on the surface of amorphous Si-(B)-C-N ceramic materials (previous Sec. 3.2), the dissociation process is investigated for the intermediate configurations at the most stable adsorption sites. The initial state corresponds to the most stable O₂ adsorption configuration, while the final state represents the stable co-adsorbed configurations of dissociated oxygen atoms. The potential energy diagrams for the dissociation of O₂ molecules on the surfaces of amorphous Si-(B)-C-N ceramic materials and Si-C-N are shown in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively. The activation barriers associated with O₂ molecule dissociation on these surfaces are summarized in Table 2, while Figs. 4 and 5 show the optimized structures for the initial, transition, and final states of the dissociation reactions. The E_{act} values characterizing O₂ dissociation on the Si-B-C-N surfaces Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄, Si₂₈B₉C₁₂N₅₃, Si₂₃B₁₁C₁₉N₄₉, Si₂₀B₁₁C₂₆N₄₃, Si₁₅B₁₃C₃₃N₃₇, Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆ are 3.27 eV, 2.51 eV, 2.37 eV, 2.25 eV, 2.21 eV, and 2.13 eV, respectively, while those characterizing O₂ dissociation on the Si-C-

Table 1

List of compositions simulated and their calculated bonding statistics. The low concentrations of Si-Si and N-N bonds are neglected. The low concentrations of double Si=N and B=C and triple C≡C and C≡N bonds are not shown separately but together with bonds of a lower order. The volume per atom (inverse atomic density) and its

Composition	Bonds per 100 atoms										$\text{\AA}^3/\text{at.}$	Source		
	Si-C	Si-N	Si=N	B-C	B=C	B-N	B=N	C-C	C=C	C≡C			C-N	C=N
Si ₃₂ B ₈ C ₆ N ₅₄	3	118		0		14	9	0	1		4	7	11.43	experiment
Si ₂₈ B ₉ C ₁₂ N ₅₃	13	91		3		16	7	3	0		3	11	11.15	interpolation
Si ₂₃ B ₁₁ C ₁₉ N ₄₉	15	70		7		17	9	3	1		12	15	10.86	interpolation
Si ₂₀ B ₁₁ C ₂₆ N ₄₃	15	55		11		15	8	6	3		8	20	10.58	interpolation
Si ₁₅ B ₁₃ C ₃₃ N ₃₇	18	43		16		15	8	12	8		9	14	10.29	interpolation
Si ₁₁ B ₁₄ C ₃₉ N ₃₆	11	31		16		22	7	17	10		22	12	10.00	experiment
Si ₄₀ C ₆ N ₅₄	11	108		–		–	–	0	1		12	14	11.43	Si-B-C-N
Si ₁₁ C ₅₃ N ₃₆	18	26		–		–	–	32	12		28	23	10.00	Si-B-C-N

Source are shown as well. See also an example of experimental verification in Fig. S1.

Fig. 1. Adsorption geometry of O₂ molecule on the surface of amorphous (a) Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄, (b) Si₂₈B₉C₁₂N₅₃, (c) Si₂₃B₁₁C₁₉N₄₉, (d) Si₂₀B₁₁C₂₆N₄₃, (e) Si₁₅B₁₃C₃₃N₃₇, (f) Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆, (g) Si₄₀C₆N₅₄ and (h) Si₁₁C₅₃N₃₆.

Table 2

Adsorption energies of O₂ molecule (an intermediate before the dissociation; E_{ads}), lengths of bonds bonding this intermediate to the surface Si/B/C/N atoms ($d_{\text{O-Si/B/C/N}}$), activation energy barriers for the subsequent O₂ dissociation ($E_{\text{act}} = E_{\text{max}} - E_{\text{ads}}$) and activated bond lengths of the transition state during this dissociation ($d_{\text{O-O}}$).

Surface	E_{ads} (eV)	$d_{\text{O-Si/B/C/N}}$ (\AA)	Interacting atoms	E_{act} (eV)	$d_{\text{O-O}}$ (\AA)
Si ₃₂ B ₈ C ₆ N ₅₄	-4.43	1.34	O-N	3.27	1.50
Si ₂₈ B ₉ C ₁₂ N ₅₃	-2.40	1.77, 1.69	O-Si/O-Si	2.51	1.97
Si ₂₃ B ₁₁ C ₁₉ N ₄₉	-2.63	1.64, 1.67	O-Si/O-Si	2.37	1.90
Si ₂₀ B ₁₁ C ₂₆ N ₄₃	-2.06	1.72, 1.74	O-Si/O-Si	2.25	1.97
Si ₁₅ B ₁₃ C ₃₃ N ₃₇	-3.05	1.73, 1.35	O-Si/O-C	2.21	2.09
Si ₁₁ B ₁₄ C ₃₉ N ₃₆	-3.70	1.38, 1.48	O-B/O-C	2.13	2.07
Si ₄₀ C ₆ N ₅₄	-4.32	1.67, 1.72	O-Si/O-Si	1.53	1.82
Si ₁₁ C ₅₃ N ₃₆	-1.19	1.71, 1.98	O-Si/O-Si	1.41	1.78

N surfaces Si₄₀C₆N₅₄, and Si₁₁C₅₃N₃₆ are 1.53 eV and 1.41 eV, respectively.

The activated O-O bond lengths are shown in the table as well. Notably, the extremal composition Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄ is characterized not only by the largest E_{ads} and E_{act} , but also by the shortest elongation of the O-O bond during the dissociation process, from 1.23 \AA in the oxygen gas phase to only 1.50 \AA . Finally, Figs. 2 and 3 visualize also the final

energies E_{final} between -5.03 eV and -7.96 eV, leading to reaction energies $E_{\text{react}} = E_{\text{final}} - E_{\text{ads}}$ between -0.50 eV and -4.16 eV. The largest E_{final} of -7.96 eV is once again associated with the extremal composition Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄. The E_{react} values confirm the exothermic character of the O₂ dissociation on all surfaces, but also indicate - beyond the present scope - that a larger set of calculations would be necessary to suppress the statistical noise of this particular quantity.

Most importantly, the activation energy barrier trend for O₂ dissociation follows the order: Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄ > Si₂₈B₉C₁₂N₅₃ > Si₂₃B₁₁C₁₉N₄₉ > Si₂₀B₁₁C₂₆N₄₃ > Si₁₅B₁₃C₃₃N₃₇ > Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆ > Si₄₀C₆N₅₄ > Si₁₁C₅₃N₃₆. In other words, the non-monotonic compositional dependencies of E_{ads} and E_{max} yield convincing monotonic dependencies of the crucial quantity $E_{\text{act}} = E_{\text{max}} - E_{\text{ads}}$, visualized in Fig. 5. These dependencies reveal that and how the elemental composition, particularly the boron content and Si/C ratio, plays a significant role in the activation energy barriers for the onset of oxidation of amorphous Si-B-C-N and Si-C-N materials. First, amorphous boron-free Si-C-N materials (Fig. 5b) exhibit lower E_{act} for O₂ dissociation compared to Si-B-C-N materials (Fig. 5a), indicating the ability of boron to shift the oxidation onset to higher temperatures. Second, E_{act} for O₂ dissociation on the surface of Si-B-C-N monotonically increases with increasing Si/C ratio (Fig. 5a), indicating that higher Si/C shifts the oxidation onset to higher temperatures. Third, E_{act} for O₂ dissociation on the surface of Si-C-N is also

Fig. 2. Potential energy diagram of dissociation of O₂ on the surface of amorphous Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄, Si₂₈B₉C₁₂N₅₃, Si₂₃B₁₁C₁₉N₄₉, Si₂₀B₁₁C₂₆N₄₃, Si₁₅B₁₃C₃₃N₃₇ and Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆. There are quantified adsorption energies of O₂ (bottom left), maximum energies of the transition state (top right) and activation energies during the dissociation (top right in round brackets).

Fig. 3. Potential energy diagram of dissociation of O₂ on the surface of amorphous Si₄₀C₆N₅₄ and Si₁₁C₅₃N₃₆. There are quantified adsorption energies of O₂ (bottom left), maximum energies of the transition state (top right) and activation energies during the dissociation (top right in round brackets).

higher at higher Si/C (Fig. 5b), although in this case the corresponding values are relatively close.

3.4. Experimental verification and discussion

Fig. 6 shows the oxidation behavior from the thermogravimetric analysis of Si-B-C-N and Si-C-N films prepared by dc reactive magnetron sputtering and then annealed up to the 1350 °C limit imposed by the Si substrate (see Ref. [4] for detailed methodology of the film preparation and characterization). Small amounts of Ar, H, and O are not included in the elemental compositions presented, so the elemental compositions do

not sum to 100 percent. Note that the compositions Si₂₈B₇C₆N₄₆ and Si₁₀B₁₂C₃₅N₃₂ can be rescaled as the extremal simulated compositions Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄ and Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆, respectively (taking into account that the number of valence electrons in the simulation cell should be even). The figure captures the oxidation in terms of mass changes: loss of N₂, CO₂ and probably also B₂O₃, only partially compensated by the mass of oxygen in SiO₂-based surface oxide layers.

Indeed, Fig. 6 highlights the effect of elemental composition, specifically the boron content and the Si/C ratio, on the (i) oxidation onset of Si-B-C-N and Si-C-N films (the key quantity for the verification of our DFT calculations) and (ii) mass changes, being a measure of oxidation

Fig. 4. Initial states (left column), transition states (middle column) and final states (right column) for dissociation of O_2 molecule on the surface of amorphous $Si_{28}B_9C_{12}N_{53}$ (a-c), $Si_{23}B_{11}C_{19}N_{49}$ (d-f), $Si_{20}B_{11}C_{26}N_{43}$ (g-i), $Si_{15}B_{13}C_{33}N_{37}$ (j-l), $Si_{32}B_8C_6N_{54}$ (m-o), $Si_{40}C_6N_{54}$ (p-r), $Si_{11}B_{14}C_{39}N_{36}$ (s-u), and $Si_{11}C_{53}N_{36}$ (v-x). The color codes are the same as in Fig. 1.

Fig. 5. The activation energy barrier of dissociation of O_2 molecule on the surface of (a) amorphous $Si_{32}B_8C_6N_{54}$, $Si_{28}B_9C_{12}N_{53}$, $Si_{23}B_{11}C_{19}N_{49}$, $Si_{20}B_{11}C_{26}N_{43}$, $Si_{15}B_{13}C_{33}N_{37}$ and $Si_{11}B_{14}C_{39}N_{36}$ and (b) amorphous $Si_{40}C_6N_{54}$ and $Si_{11}C_{53}N_{36}$.

rate, at temperatures above the oxidation onset (beyond the scope of the DFT calculations). First, the boron-containing materials $Si_{28}B_7C_6N_{46}$ and $Si_{10}B_{12}C_{35}N_{32}$ exhibit oxidation onsets at significantly higher temperatures (let us recall high E_{act} in Fig. 5a) than the boron-free materials $Si_{25}C_{26}N_{42}$ and $Si_9C_{61}N_{26}$ (low E_{act} in Fig. 5b). Second, higher Si/C ratio shifts the oxidation onset to higher temperatures at a presence of B (compare $Si_{28}B_7C_6N_{46}$ with $Si_{10}B_{12}C_{35}N_{32}$, in agreement with the trend in Fig. 5a) as well as at the absence of B (compare $Si_{25}C_{26}N_{42}$ with $Si_9C_{61}N_{26}$, in agreement with the trend in Fig. 5b). Quantitatively, the changes of both E_{ads} and oxidation onset due to B incorporation are

larger than those due to enhanced Si/C ratio (another agreement of the modelling and the experiment).

Note that the most oxidation resistant B-containing Si-rich composition $Si_{28}B_7C_6N_{46}$ actually exhibits almost horizontal thermogravimetric curve up to the 1350 °C substrate limit. The thickness of the surface oxide layer was below 20 nm after the presented annealing of a film deposited on Si to 1350 °C, and it exceeded 1 μm only after an annealing of a film deposited on SiC to 1700 °C. See Fig. S2 for the corresponding images from transmission electron microscopy and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, constituting a qualitative

Fig. 6. Thermogravimetric analysis (heating in dry air at a rate of 10 °C/min) of as-deposited Si-B-C-N (solid curves) and boron-free Si-C-N (dashed curves) films up to the 1350 °C limit imposed by the Si substrate. There are Si-rich compositions (red curves) as well as C-rich compositions (blue curves). The background, representing substrate oxidation, has been carefully subtracted.

confirmation what is happening with the films during the annealing as well as the quantified information about the thickness of the surface oxide layer.

The presented findings are complementary to and point in the same direction as those based on the atomic-scale view. Although Si and C have the same number of valence electrons, Si forms only single bonds while C forms many double and triple bonds (Table 1). Thus, higher Si/C ratio leads to higher average coordination number of the amorphous networks [51] and higher overall strength of bonds which have to be broken during diffusion or oxidation. That said, some presence of C can be accepted for reasons such as enhanced amount of diffusion needed for crystallization and/or for decomposition reactions, as a consequence of preferring industry-friendly preparation techniques such as sputtering B₄C instead of B [19], and due to the parallel efforts to optimize also some other functional property. The latter may lead to trade-offs such as lowering the Si/C ratio until the material starts to be reasonably electrically conductive [54]. Presence of B (despite less valence electrons) can support the network interconnection and stability as well: owing to the high affinity of B to N, some of the lonepairs of valence electrons associated N in Si-C-N convert to bonding electrons in Si-B-C-N [51]. Boron contents on the order of 10 % have been successfully utilized for the present purpose (8 % [51], ≥9 % [50], 10–12 % [19] or 16.7 % [41], at various ratios of the other elements), while higher B contents are sometimes utilized [46] but have been reported to harm the oxidation resistance [41].

4. Conclusions

Amorphous Si-(B)-C-N alloys are widely recognized for their exceptional oxidation resistance and ability to retain functional properties at elevated temperatures. The influence of boron incorporation and varied Si/C ratio on the oxidation onset (not to be confused with the oxidation rate at temperatures above this onset) of Si-(B)-C-N has been investigated by density functional theory simulations. Various adsorption sites and initial geometries sites were examined to understand the O₂ adsorption behavior and to identify the most stable configurations. The activation energy barriers for the subsequent O₂ dissociation decrease from 3.27 to 1.41 eV in the order: Si₃₂B₈C₆N₅₄ > Si₂₈B₉C₁₂N₅₃ > Si₂₃B₁₁C₁₉N₄₉ > Si₂₀B₁₁C₂₆N₄₃ > Si₁₅B₁₃C₃₃N₃₇ > Si₁₁B₁₄C₃₉N₃₆ > Si₄₀C₆N₅₄ > Si₁₁C₅₃N₃₆. The enhancement of this activation energy barrier due to boron incorporation and/or enhanced

Si/C ratio is important for shifting the decomposition reactions to higher temperatures. The *ab initio* results are in an excellent agreement with experimental results of thermogravimetric analysis of thin films prepared by dc magnetron sputtering. Collectively, the results emphasize the roles of individual elements in optimizing the functional properties of Si-(B)-C-N, provide new quantitative information about previously unknown activation energies for their oxidation, in turn facilitate the comparison of Si-(B)-C-N ceramic materials with other materials, and contribute to the full utilization of their application potential.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jemal Yimer Dame: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jiri Houska:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the project Quantum materials for applications in sustainable technologies (QM4ST), funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004572 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. Computational resources were provided by the e-INFRA CZ project (ID:90254), supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2025.113653>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] H.-P. Baldus, M. Jansen, Novel high-performance ceramics-amorphous inorganic networks from molecular precursors, *Angew. Chem.* 36 (1997) 328–343, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.199703281>.
- [2] R. Riedel, A. Klenzle, W. Dressler, L. Ruwisch, J. Bill, F. Aldinger, A silicoboron carbonitride ceramic stable to 2000 °C, *Nature* 382 (1996) 796–798, <https://doi.org/10.1038/382796a0>.
- [3] M.A. Rooke, P.M.A. Sherwood, Surface studies of potentially oxidation protective Si-B-N-C films for carbon fibers, *Chem. Mater.* 9 (1997) 285–296, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm960365b>.
- [4] J. Vlcek, S. Potocky, J. Cizek, J. Houska, M. Kormunda, P. Zeman, V. Perina, J. Zemek, Y. Setsuhara, S. Konuma, Reactive magnetron sputtering of hard Si-B-C-N films with a high-temperature oxidation resistance, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A* 23 (2005) 1513–1522, <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.2049298>.
- [5] A. Vijayakumar, A.P. Warren, R.M. Todi, K.B. Sundaram, Photoluminescence from RF sputtered Si-C-B-N thin films, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Electron.* 20 (2009) 144–148, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-008-9667-4>.
- [6] V.M. Vishnyakov, A.P. Ehasarian, V.V. Vishnyakov, P. Hovsepian, J.S. Colligon, Amorphous boron containing silicon carbo-nitrides created by ion sputtering, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 206 (2011) 149–154, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2011.07.002>.
- [7] P. Zhang, D. Jia, Z. Yang, X. Duan, Y. Zhou, Progress of a novel non-oxide Si-B-C-N ceramic and its matrix composites, *J. Adv. Ceram.* 1 (2012) 157–178, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40145-012-0017-x>.
- [8] P.V. Kiryukhantsev-Korneev, A.N. Sheveyko, E.A. Levashov, D.V. Shtansky, Investigation of the Si-B-C-N coatings deposited by magnetron sputtering of SiBC targets, *Russ. J. Non-Ferrous Met.* 56 (2015) 540–547, <https://doi.org/10.3103/S1067821215050077>.

- [9] R. Pan, S. Kovacevic, T. Lina, P. He, D.P. Sekulic, S.D. Mesarovic, Z. Yang, Y. Shen, H. Wei, Control of residual stresses in 2Si-B-3C-N and Nb joints by the Ag-Cu-Ti + Mo composite interlayer, *Mater. Des.* 99 (2016) 193–200, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2016.03.072>.
- [10] G. Zhao, P. Hu, S. Zhou, G. Chen, Y. An, Y. Cheng, J. An, X. Zhang, W. Han, Ordered silica nanoparticles grown on a three-dimensional carbon fiber architecture substrate with siliconborocarbonitride ceramic as a thermal barrier coating, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 8 (2016) 4216–4225, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.5b12140>.
- [11] A. Viard, D. Fonblanc, D. Lopez-Ferber, M. Schmidt, A. Lale, C. Durif, M. Balestrat, F. Rossignol, M. Weinmann, R. Riedel, S. Bernard, Polymer derived Si-B-C-N ceramics: 30 Years of research, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 20 (2018) 1–31, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.201800360>.
- [12] X. Ji, S. Wang, C. Shao, H. Wang, High-temperature corrosion behavior of Si-B-C-N fibers for aerospace applications, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (2018) 19712–19720, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b04497>.
- [13] D. Jia, B. Liang, Z. Yang, Y. Zhou, Metastable Si-B-C-N ceramics and their matrix composites developed by inorganic route based on mechanical alloying: Fabrication, microstructures, properties and their relevant basic scientific issues, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 98 (2018) 1–67, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2018.05.006>.
- [14] C. Luo, Y. Tang, T. Jiao, J. Kong, High-temperature stable and metal-free electromagnetic wave-absorbing Si-B-C-N ceramics derived from carbon-rich hyperbranched polyborosilazanes, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (2018) 28051–28061, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b07879>.
- [15] G. Shao, J. Jiang, M. Jiang, J. Su, W. Liu, H. Wang, H. Xu, H. Lit, R. Zhang, Polymer-derived Si-B-C-N ceramic pressure sensor with excellent sensing performance, *J. Adv. Ceram.* 9 (2020) 374–379, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40145-020-0377-6>.
- [16] S. Chen, Q. Zhang, X. Luan, R. Yu, S. Zhang, L. Cheng, Sapphire optical fiber with Si-B-C-N coating prepared by chemical vapor deposition for high-temperature sensing applications, *Thin Solid Films* 709 (2020) 138242, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2020.138242>.
- [17] Q. Hanniet, M. Boussmen, J. Barés, V. Huon, I. Iatsunskyi, E. Coy, M. Bechelany, C. Gervais, D. Voiry, P. Miele, C. Salameh, Investigation of polymer-derived Si-(B)-C-N ceramic/reduced graphene oxide composite systems as active catalysts towards the hydrogen evolution reaction, *Sci. Rep.* 10 (2020) 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78558-x>.
- [18] J. Houska, J. Kalas, J. Vlcek, M.M.M. Bilek, D.R. McKenzie, Effect of implanted argon on hardness of novel magnetron sputtered Si-B-C-N materials: Experiments and ab initio simulations, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* 19 (2007) 196228, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/19/19/196228>.
- [19] J. Vlcek, P. Calta, P. Steidl, P. Zeman, R. Cerstvy, J. Houska, J. Kohout, Pulsed reactive magnetron sputtering of high-temperature Si-B-C-N films with high optical transparency, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 226 (2013) 34–39, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2013.03.033>.
- [20] E. Aschauer, T. Wojcik, P. Polcik, O. Hunold, M. Arndt, V. Dalbauer, P. H. Mayrhofer, P. Felfel, H. Riedl, Ultra-high oxidation resistance of nano-structured thin films, *Mater. Des.* 201 (2021) 109499, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2021.109499>.
- [21] D. Ni, Y. Cheng, J. Zhang, J.X. Liu, J. Zou, B. Chen, H. Wu, H. Li, S. Dong, J. Han, X. Zhang, Q. Fu, G.J. Zhang, Advances in ultra-high temperature ceramics, composites, and coatings, *J. Adv. Ceram.* 11 (2022) 1–56, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40145-021-0550-6>.
- [22] J. Houska, J. Vlcek, S. Potocky, V. Perina, Influence of substrate bias voltage on structure and properties of hard Si-B-C-N films prepared by reactive magnetron sputtering, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* 16 (2007) 29–36, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diamond.2006.03.012>.
- [23] J. Kalas, R. Vernhes, S. Hreben, J. Vlcek, J.E. Klemberg-Sapieha, L. Martinu, High-temperature stability of the mechanical and optical properties of Si-B-C-N films prepared by magnetron sputtering, *Thin Solid Films* 518 (2009) 174–179, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2009.06.017>.
- [24] P.A. Ramakrishnan, Y.T. Wang, D. Balzar, L. An, C. Haluschka, R. Riedel, A. M. Hermann, Siliconboron-carbonitride ceramics: A class of high-temperature, dopable electronic materials, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 78 (2001) 3076–3078, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1370540>.
- [25] A. Vijayakumar, R.M. Todi, K.B. Sundaram, Amorphous-Si-C-B-N based metal-semiconductor-metal photodetector for high-temperature applications, *IEEE Electron Device Lett.* 28 (2007) 713–715, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LED.2007.902083>.
- [26] S. Lv, Q. Yang, F. Ye, R. Yu, X. Luan, L. Cheng, Sapphire optical fiber with (BN/SiBCN)_n coating prepared by chemical vapor deposition for high-temperature sensing applications, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (2024) 46557–46565, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.09.008>.
- [27] C. Wu, X. Pan, F. Lin, Z. Cui, X. Li, G. Chen, X. Liu, Y. He, G. He, Z. Hai, Q. Chen, D. Sun, High-temperature electrical properties of polymer-derived ceramic SiBCN thin films fabricated by direct writing, *Ceram. Int.* 48 (2022) 15293–15302, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2022.02.063>.
- [28] Q. Yan, S. Chen, H. Shi, X. Wang, S. Meng, J. Li, Fabrication of polymer-derived SiBCN ceramic temperature sensor with excellent sensing performance, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 43 (2023) 7373–7380, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2023.08.009>.
- [29] Z. Li, Z. Gao, X. Zhang, Y. Liu, P.J. Withers, P. Xiao, Oxidation behavior and subsequent mechanical properties of SiC/BN/SiBCN composite after exposure to steam at high temperature, *Corros. Sci.* 243 (2025) 112584, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2024.112584>.
- [30] Z. Niu, D. Li, D. Jia, Z. Yang, K. Lin, Y. Wang, P. Colombo, R. Riedel, Y. Zhou, Three-dimensional PDC-SiBCN network in MA-SiBCN ceramics: Toughening-reinforcing effect and oxidation barrier, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 45 (2025) 117053, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2024.117053>.
- [31] J. Liu, Y. Fenga, C. Liu, Y. Tong, H. Sun, H. Peng, S. Wu, J. Lu, H. Gong, X. Guo, J. Li, Novel SiBCN composite fibers with broadband and strong electromagnetic wave absorption performance, *J. Alloys Compd.* 912 (2022) 165190, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2022.165190>.
- [32] Y. Wang, C. Luo, Y. Wu, X. Hu, L. Wang, X. Chen, M. Chao, G. Liu, Y. Hu, L. Yan, High temperature stable, amorphous SiBCN microwave absorption ceramics with tunable carbon structures derived from divinylbenzene crosslinked hyperbranched polyborosilazane, *Carbon* 213 (2023) 118189, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2023.118189>.
- [33] H. Liu, Y. Zhang, X. Liu, W. Duan, M. Li, Q. Zhou, S. Li, G. Wang, G. Han, Additive manufacturing of nanocellulose/polyborosilazane derived CNFs-SiBCN ceramic metamaterials for ultra-broadband electromagnetic absorption, *Chem. Eng.* 433 (2022) 133743, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.133743>.
- [34] W. Zhu, Z. Chen, J. Liang, D. Su, A laminated carbon nanotubes/silicon boron carbonitride film for high-efficiency electromagnetic interference shielding with oxidation resistance, *Carbon* 197 (2022) 65–75, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2022.06.018>.
- [35] B. Ren, Y. Deng, Y. Jia, L. Han, X. Wang, H. Li, Achieving broadband electromagnetic absorption at a wide temperature range up to 1273 K by metamaterial design on polymer-derived SiC-BN@CNT ceramic composites, *Chem. Eng.* 478 (2023) 147251, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.147251>.
- [36] J. Jiang, L. Yan, Y. Xue, J. Li, C. Zhang, X. Hu, A. Guo, H. Du, J. Liu, Lightweight and thermally insulating polymer-derived SiBCN/SiCNw ceramic aerogel with enhanced electromagnetic wave absorbing performance, *Chem. Eng.* 482 (2024) 148878, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.148878>.
- [37] J. Jiang, L. Yan, J. Li, Y. Xue, C. Zhang, X. Hu, A. Guo, H. Du, J. Liu, Lightweight, thermally insulating SiBCN/Al₂O₃ ceramic aerogel with enhanced high-temperature resistance and electromagnetic wave absorption performance, *Chem. Eng.* 501 (2024) 157656, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.157656>.
- [38] M. Zhang, Y. Liu, J. Zhang, X. Chen, F. Li, D. Li, D. Jia, R. Riedel, Y. Zhou, DFT analysis of the effect of Zr on the structure and mechanical property of amorphous SiBCN ceramics, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (2024) 13949–13959, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.01.312>.
- [39] Y. Lyu, Y. Cheng, G. Zhao, M. Wang, G. Chen, X. Zhang, W. Han, Modification of SiBCN by Zr atom and its effect on ablative resistance of Cf/SiBCN(Zr) composites, *Compos. B Eng.* 253 (2023) 110511, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110511>.
- [40] J.C. Jiang, Y. Shen, P. Zeman, M. Prochazka, J. Vlcek, E.I. Meletis, Effects of Y and Ho doping on microstructure evolution during oxidation of extraordinary stable Hf-B-Si-Y/Ho-C-N films up to 1500 °C, *Mater. Des.* 237 (2024) 112589, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112589>.
- [41] D. Li, Z. Yang, D. Jia, X. Duan, D. Cai, S. Wang, J. Yuan, Y. Zhou, D. Yu, Y. Tian, High-temperature oxidation resistance of dense amorphous boron-rich Si-B-C-N monoliths, *Corros. Sci.* 157 (2019) 312–323, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2019.06.001>.
- [42] M.K. Ciniulk, T.A. Parthasarathy, Characterization of oxidized polymer-derived SiBCN fibers, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 84 (2001) 2197–2202, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.2001.tb00987.x>.
- [43] B. Liang, Z.H. Yang, D.C. Jia, J.C. Rao, D.L. Yu, Y.J. Tian, Q. Li, Y. Miao, Q.S. Zhu, Y. Zhou, Amorphous siliconboron carbonitride monoliths resistant to flowing air up to 1800 °C, *Corros. Sci.* 109 (2016) 162–173, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2016.03.026>.
- [44] D. Li, Z. Yang, D. Jia, S. Wang, X. Duan, Q. Zhu, Y. Miao, J. Rao, Y. Zhou, High-temperature oxidation behavior of dense Si-B-C-N monoliths: Carbon-content dependent oxidation structure, kinetics and mechanisms, *Corros. Sci.* 124 (2017) 103–120, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2017.05.013>.
- [45] B. Liang, D. Jia, Y. Miao, Q. Zhu, X. Liao, Z. Yang, Y. Zhou, High temperature oxidation kinetics of amorphous siliconboron carbonitride monoliths and silica scale growth mechanisms determined by SIMS, *Corros. Sci.* 122 (2017) 100–107, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2017.04.002>.
- [46] I.S. Merenkov, H. Katsui, M.N. Khomyakov, V.S. Sulyaeva, R.V. Pushkarev, R. Tu, T. Goto, M.L. Koshinova, Extraordinary synergetic effect of precursors in laser CVD deposition of SiBCN films, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 39 (2019) 5123–5131, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2019.08.006>.
- [47] Q. Hanniet, E. Petit, S. Calas-Etienne, P. Etienne, K. Aissou, C. Gervais, P. Miele, B. Charlot, C. Salameh, Rational design of Si-B-C-N microstructures using direct photolithography of patternable preceramic photoresists, *Mater. Des.* 223 (2022) 111234, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2022.111234>.
- [48] A.H. Tavakoli, P. Gerstel, J.A. Golczewski, J. Bill, Effect of boron on the crystallization of amorphous Si-(B)-C-N polymer-derived ceramics, *J. Non. Cryst. Solids* 355 (2009) 2381–2389, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnoncrysol.2009.08.010>.
- [49] A.H. Tavakoli, P. Gerstel, J.A. Golczewski, J. Bill, Kinetic effect of boron on the crystallization of Si₃N₄ in Si-B-C-N polymer-derived ceramics, *J. Mater. Res.* 26 (2011) 600–608, <https://doi.org/10.1557/jmr.2010.53>.
- [50] A. Müller, P. Gerstel, M. Weinmann, J. Bill, F. Aldinger, Correlation of boron content and high temperature stability in Si-B-C-N ceramics II, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 21 (2001) 2171–2177, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2219\(00\)00344-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2219(00)00344-7).
- [51] J. Houska, J. Vlcek, S. Hreben, M.M.M. Bilek, D.R. McKenzie, Effect of B and the Si/C ratio on high-temperature stability of Si-B-C-N materials, *Europhys. Lett.* 76 (2006) 512–518, <https://doi.org/10.1209/epl/12006-10283-5>.

- [52] Y. Liu, Y. Zhou, D. Jia, Z. Yang, D. Li, B. Liu, Unveiling structural features and mechanical properties of amorphous Si₂BC₃N by density functional theory, *J. Mater. Sci.* 139 (2023) 103–112, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2022.09.003>.
- [53] Y. Liu, Y. Zhou, D. Jia, Z. Yang, W. Duan, D. Li, S. Li, R. Riedel, B. Liu, Composition-dependent structural characteristics and mechanical properties of amorphous SiBCN ceramics by ab-initio calculations, *J. Adv. Ceram.* 12 (2023) 984–1000, <https://doi.org/10.26599/JAC.2023.9220733>.
- [54] J. Houska, S. Kos, Si-B-C-N materials for high-temperature applications: Atomistic origin of electrical conductivity, *J. Appl. Phys.* 108 (2010) 083711, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3493265>.
- [55] CPMD, <http://www.cpmc.org>, Copyright IBM Corp 1990-2024, Copyright MPI für Festkörperforschung Stuttgart 1997-2001.
- [56] G. Kresse, J. Furthmüller, Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set, *Phys. Rev. B* 54 (1996) 11169–11186, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.0c01375>.
- [57] J.P. Perdew, K. Burke, M. Ernzerhof, Generalized gradient approximation made simple, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 77 (1996) 3865–3868, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b15784>.
- [58] G. Kresse, D. Joubert, From ultrasoft pseudopotentials to the projector augmented-wave method, *PhysRevB* 59 (1999) 1758–1775, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.59.1758>.
- [59] G. Henkelman, B.P. Uberuaga, H. Jónsson, Climbing image nudged elastic band method for finding saddle points and minimum energy paths, *J. Chem. Phys.* 113 (2000) 9901–9904, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1329672>.
- [60] J. Houska, Maximum achievable N content in atom-by-atom growth of amorphous Si-B-C-N materials, *Materials* 14 (2021) 5744, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14195744>.